

Original Research Article

Bullying Protective Program and Its Effect on Self-efficacy and Self-esteem among Nursing Students

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Abstract

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Bullying among nurses and nursing students is a serious issue and generates a negative culture that threatens the ethics of nursing professionals and causes burnout or turnover among nurses. Hence, we must seriously consider measures to prevent it. Moreover, self-efficacy and self-esteem is crucial for the ability and performance of nursing students in the work environment. The aim of this study was to investigate the effect of applying bullying protective program on self-efficacy and self-esteem among nursing students. A quasi-experimental research design one group pre-test, post-test and follow-up test was used. All family and community health nursing students (221) who enrolled in the fourth year-second semester of the academic year (2018-2019) at the faculty of nursing who agreed to be part in this study were included. Two tools were utilized which are General Self-Efficacy Scale (GSE) and Rosenberg's Global Self-esteem Scale, in addition to program implementation. There were statistically significant differences in both self-efficacy and self-esteem levels before and after the bullying protective program. There were a highly statistical significant improvement in the different levels of both self-esteem and self-efficacy immediately after bullying protective program and after 3 months (follow-up test) among nursing students compared to before the program where ($p = 0.000$). Implementation of a bullying protective program has a positive effect on improving self-efficacy and self-esteem of nursing students. Nursing curricula should integrate the concept of bullying and how to confront it in a professional manner. Also, the nursing college should set policies to eradicate the occurrence of bullying in the workplace, which creates a positive influence on the learning environment and the nursing profession as a whole.

Keywords: Bullying, Nursing students, Self-efficacy, Self-esteem

INTRODUCTION

Self-efficacy is considered one of the greatest powerful factors affecting the quality of clinical practice and perceived occupational advantages (Cheng et al., 2020). Self-efficacy is the confidence of people in their competence to achieve a desired goal (Richard and Carrie, 2018). It is also people's beliefs about their competences to create chosen levels of performance that affect their lives. Self-efficacy beliefs determine how people feel, think, motivate themselves and behave

(Viswam-Athira et al., 2017). From another point of view, Bandura (1986) as cited by Pedrazza et al., (2013) presented a proper definition of self-efficacy: "as people's decisions of their competences to establish and perform courses of action.

Nursing students' self-efficacy is a predictor for their didactic development. Students, who deem that they can be successful in their studies, are more confident (Sarikoc and Oksuz, 2017). Nursing students with

higher levels of self-efficacy used proper handling strategies when confronted with strain from tasks and overload during their clinical experience. Individuals with greater self-efficacy in nursing practice are more predictable to not see stress as a stressor and alternatively utilize problem-solving skills (Zhao et al., 2015).

The basic belief behind the theory of self-efficacy is that persons are more likely to be involved in actions for which they have high self-efficacy and are expert in those activities; and less likely to involve in activities they are not proficient (Mangi et al., 2019). Therefore, self-efficacy can be improved by achieving minor tasks and acquiring confidence in one's ability and help from a qualified individual or an associate (Van Damme et al., 2011).

Self-efficacy in nursing practice is the person's belief that they have the essential information, talents, and capabilities to deliver safe, quality patient care (Wolff et al., 2010). Self-efficient persons select more pliant, selective, and inspiring things in fulfilling objectives; they are more accountable and often impute their fail to insufficient knowledge and skills (Rahmati, 2015). People who perceive themselves as efficacious are realistic about their capacities and do not overestimate the difficulties they encounter. Also, people with great levels of self-efficacy use problem-solving strategies to manage workplace issues and job demands, while those with low levels of self-efficacy resort to more dysfunctional coping styles (Reid, 2012).

Self-esteem is one of the greatest essential features for development, talent and innovation; it penetrates all thoughts, opinions, excitements, dreams, beliefs and objects of an individual. It is well-defined as how persons think about themselves and how they feel about themselves in their social and academic life and how close and harmonized their own ideal self and actual self (Mirzaei-Alavijeh, et al., 2018). Self-esteem has been known as a judgment of oneself other than an attitude toward the self. It encompasses beliefs and feelings such as the feeling of achievement, despair, pride and shame (Kumar, 2020). Hence, Rosenberg (1986) as cited by Valizadeh et al., (2016) considers self-esteem as a constant characteristic of adults, while current researchers believe that it is a developmental process that is affected by new conditions.

High levels of self-esteem are prognostic of good consequences such as academic success, social life, physical and psychological health, satisfaction with job. But low level of self-esteem indicates self-rejection, self-dissatisfaction, and self-contempt, as the person deficiencies respect for self (Silvestri et al., 2018). Low self-esteem has been connected with undesirable consequences, such as depression, anxiety, and anger, along with aggressive and violent behaviors (Teng et al., 2015). Also, low self-esteem can make a person victim of bullying or leading an individual to become a bully (Arand, 2019).

Bullying is a familiar and constant problem against nurses and nursing students (Gillespie et al., 2017 and Kang, 2018). Al bakoo (2019) illustrated that bullying phenomenon is one of the greatest difficult problems faced by schools, in spite of the fact that all students have the right to have education in a safe environment, a global phenomenon that speaks not only in the health care sector but also in nursing education.

Previous studies have revealed that nursing students have the highest risk of experiencing bullying from experienced nurses (Park, 2013; Abd El Rahman, 2014; Ren et al., 2015). The incidence of bullying experience differs through nations, culture, the definition and instrument used to assess bullying. Approximately four fifths of nursing students experienced at least one bullying behavior in the previous six months in clinical sites (Ren et al., 2015) and (86.7%) of nursing students experienced bullying in Korea (Park, 2013). Likewise, in Egypt, Abd El Rahman, (2014) identified that most of nursing students (88 %) experienced bullying behaviors. In addition, the current estimates of the incidence of bullying among the nursing workforce was about (30%) (Ganz et al., 2015). Furthermore, Berry et al., (2012) revealed a higher incidence of bullying against newly licensed nurses (72.6%) of the sample had experienced bullying.

Bullying defined by Sullivan (2000) as cited by Darney et al. (2013) is a conscious and deliberate act of violence and / or manipulation by one or more individuals or persons against another individual or group. It takes several forms that can be classified as verbal, bodily and relational. Bullying is a recurring action, not a one-time occurrence. Victims of bullying are injured or distressed in the face of repeated attacks against which they cannot defend themselves. The end result of bullying behavior is the empowerment and gratification of one side and the suffering or distress of the other (Oyaziwo, 2006).

Nursing students' bullying experiences should be considered extremely as they have a long-term influence on their self-esteem and identity accompanied by undesirably affecting their future career as a nurse. Bullying of nursing students during the clinical location is initiated by numerous circumstantial conditions such as undesirable nursing work environment and hierarchical organizational culture (Kang et al., 2018). The main targets of the adverse influence of bullying are the nursing students themselves, but the effect can spread to family and friends, and even society as a whole. In addition, bullying leads to a negative culture that threatens the ethics of nursing professionals and causes burnout or turnover among nurses (Kang, 2018).

Studies have confirmed that bullied students tend to feel detached from school, have inferior academic achievement, low self-esteem, higher levels of anxiety and depression and increased hazard of substance abuse (Arsenault, 2017). Because bullying appears to be widespread within the nursing profession, we should

concern about various measures to manage it including primary and secondary and along with tertiary interventions. Primary intervention is to avoid bullying, secondary is to successfully survive with it and tertiary is to restore the negative consequences of bullying (Hershcovis et al., 2015). So, interventions are crucial to prepare nursing students to avoid and alleviate the bullying they will experience in their nursing practice (Gillespie et al., 2017).

Significance of the Study

Self-esteem, as one of the primary factors for nurses' self-awareness, is of extreme importance to the physical and psychological health and professional growth of nurses. Because of the particular nature of the health institution, high turnover rate, low work satisfaction, and an unsatisfactory sense of self-worth have become public problems both locally and globally, therefore, increasing the self-esteem of nurses is of a major importance in steadying the nursing group and enhancing the quality of practical services (We et al., 2015; Qian, 2017; He et al., 2019).

Based on the literature review and clinical experiences of researchers, nursing students devote a prolonged time in their clinical settings to acquire nursing skills. Hence, they are more vulnerable to experience workplace aggression, harassment and bullying. Likewise, Hopkins et al. (2014) stated that more than (57%) of students had experienced intangible violence during clinical setting. In addition, Wang et al. (2018) stated that bullying has been proved to reduce self-confidence and productivity. Moreover, it makes students feel frustrated which leads to a change in their performance and effectiveness within the academic framework. In Egypt, there is a clear gap in intervention-based studies about bullying among nursing students during the final year of study that can be filled by the results of this study. So, this study was carried out to investigate the effect of applying bullying protective program on self-efficacy and self-esteem among nursing students.

Aim of the study

The aim of the existing study was to investigate the effect of applying a bullying protective program on self-efficacy and self-esteem among nursing students.

Hypotheses

1. There is a positive association between bullying protective program and self-efficacy among nursing students.

2. There is a positive correlation between bullying protective program and self-esteem among nursing students.

SUBJECTS AND METHODS

Research Design

A quasi-experimental research design one group pre-test, post-test and follow-up test was used to perform this study.

Study Setting

The present research was accomplished at the Faculty of Nursing, Menoufia University, which is affiliated to Ministry of Higher Education, Egypt.

Study Subject

All family and community health nursing students (221) who registered in the fourth year - second semester of the academic year (2018-2019) at the faculty of nursing who approved to share in this study were involved. The researchers selected family and community health nursing students as those students experience their first contact with different groups and classes of society during home visit as a clinical area where control over surroundings environment is challenging.

Instruments of the Study

Two tools were used for data collection, besides the socio-demographic data. "These were General Self-Efficacy Scale (GSE) and Rosenberg's Global Self-esteem Scale".

Instrument One: It consisted of two portions as the followings

Part 1: Socio-demographic data

A structured socio-demographic questionnaire designed by the researchers to obtain demographic data of nursing students including "age, gender, marital status and residency".

Part 2: General Self-Efficacy Scale (GSE)

It is a self-reported measure developed by Schwarzer and Jerusalem (1995) to explore the nursing students'

level of self-efficacy. It was translated into Arabic by the researcher and tested for content validity. It comprised of 10 items. "The subjects respond with a 4-point Likert scale, which are: Not at all true (1), hardly true (2), moderately true (3), exactly true (4)". The whole score is estimated by finding the sum of all items. "For the GSE, the total score ranges between (10 and 40), scores were graded as follows; scores (10- 24) means low self-efficacy, scores from (25-34) = moderate self-efficacy, and scores from (35-40) means high self-efficacy".

Instrument Two: Rosenberg's Global Self-esteem Scale

It is developed by Rosenberg (1965). "A ten item Likert scale measures global self-worth by measuring both positive and negative feelings about the self". "All items are responded using a 4-point Likert scale format ranges from strongly agree to strongly disagree". "Scoring items 2, 5, 6, 8, 9 are reverse scored". Give "Strongly Disagree 1 point", "Disagree, 2 points", "Agree, 3 points", and "Strongly Agree, 4 points". Sum scores for all ten items. Keep scores on a continuous scale. "Higher scores indicate higher self-esteem". "The total score ranges between (0 and 30) which were categorized as follows; scores below 20 means, low self-esteem; scores from (20- 24) = moderate self- efficacy and more than 25= high self- efficacy".

Tools Reliability

"The internal consistency of the questionnaire was calculated using Cronbach's alpha coefficients". "The reliability of the tools were done using test - retest reliability and proved to be strongly reliable was between (0.76 and 0.90) for General Self-Efficacy Scale (GSE) and at (0.7222) for Rosenberg's Global Self-esteem Scale".

Tools Validity

The data collection tools were translated into Arabic and reviewed for its content validity by 5 experts specialized in the field of nursing administration, mental health nursing and community health nursing to test content validity of the study tools. Modification was made in accordance with the panel' judgment on the clearness of statements and appropriateness of content. In addition, the program content was reviewed by the same panel and the necessary adjustment was made according to their decisions.

Procedures

Ethical approval was attained from an ethical research committee of the Faculty of Nursing, Menoufia University. An official approval was attained from Dean of the Faculty of Nursing, Menoufia University. The study aim was explained to each nursing student before starting the program. An oral consent was gained from subjects to be part in the study, then the nursing students were asked to fill the questionnaire, every nursing student was spent 20-30 minutes to complete the questionnaire. The researchers told the nursing students that all information collected will be used only for research purpose, and the study results will be published in aggregates. A pilot study was accomplished on 12 nursing students to estimate the time required for filling out the sheet and also to check clarity and practicability of the tools. The pilot study sample was omitted from the total study sample. Based on the pilot study results, the necessary modification and clarification of some questions were done. The data collection phases of this study were accomplished in four months from the beginning of February 2019 to the end of May 2019. The subjects were distributed into 5 groups; each of them consisted of (44) nursing students except one group that had (45) nursing students. The period of program implementation was four weeks then the post-test was given (General Self-Efficacy Scale and Rosenberg's Global Self-esteem Scale) to them immediately after the end of the program sessions and after 3 months follow up test was done for them to investigate the effect of applying bullying protective program on self-efficacy and self-esteem among nursing students. The researchers collected the data from 1pm to 4pm. One day weekly for each group in accordance with their academic load. Implementation of this study passed into four phases (pre assessment phase (pretest), implementation phase (training program), reassessment phase (post-test) and finally evaluation phase (follow-up test).

Phase (1): Pre assessment phase: (measure 1)

Once the approval was attained to conduct this study, a comfortable, private place was chosen for the interview. Orientation was done about the researchers' name, purpose, content and significance of this study. Assessment was done "using socio-demographic questionnaire, General Self-Efficacy Scale (GSE) and Rosenberg's Global Self-esteem Scale for all nursing students".

Phase (2): Implementation Phase

The planned bullying protective program was implemented

in four consecutive weekly sessions that lasted approximately 150 to 180 minutes. This was achieved through several teaching methods such as lecture, discussions, brain storming, giving examples and modeling. "Data show, video and pictures were used as media to facilitate explanation". At the end of each session, summary, feedback, further clarifications were done for vague items.

Phase (3): Post Assessment Phase: (measure 2)

Reassessment was done using "General Self-Efficacy Scale (GSE) and Rosenberg's Global Self-esteem Scale for all nursing students".

Phase (4): Follow - up Phase: (measure 3)

Evaluation was done by using "General Self-Efficacy Scale (GSE) and Rosenberg's Global Self-esteem Scale for all nursing students".

The planned bullying protective program was implemented in four weeks - one day per week and two sessions per day for each group as the followings:

Day I: Session 1: Introduction and orientation

It is an introductory session for the identification, integration of the group, clarification of purpose and the allowed schedule for the program. Orienting the nursing students with the program sessions and its rules which includes: confirming the privacy and confidentiality of research information, commitment to sessions dates and time, avoiding interruptions while others talk, avoiding sarcasm about other' opinions and applying essential activities during every session. Then the pretest was done using, socio-demographic questionnaire, General Self-Efficacy Scale (GSE) and Rosenberg's Global Self-esteem Scale (pre intervention assessment).

Day I: Session 2: Overview of bullying phenomenon

It concerned with detailed explanation about concept, causes, forms, signs and side effect of bullying behavior. Then the researcher explained ways of protecting against bullying which include (1) the development and improvement of self-esteem. (2) Training in assertive behavior. (3) How to handle bullying phenomenon.

Day II: Session 1: Self-development and improvement

The researchers explained ways of self-development in the following dimensions. (1) Cognitive through reading

and visiting libraries. (2) Social through visiting relatives and friends and sharing their occasions (3) Health through eating balanced diet, enough sleep and performing simple exercise daily (4) Personal through trying to discard bad habits e.g. smoking, anger. (5) Family through spending time and traveling with family. (6) Spiritual dimension through performing prayers and honoring parents. Then the researchers clarified steps of self-improvement as (a) Look at the positive side of your life. (b) Stop comparing yourself with others. (c) Focus on your positive attributes and develop it. (d) Keep smiling. (e) Focus on regular exercise as it enhances your physical and psychological health. (f) Remember that all of us make mistakes but we should learn from our mistakes.

Day II: Session 2: Improving self-awareness and self-esteem

It focused on comprehensive clarification about self-awareness (definition, goal and methods of self-evaluation. The researchers motivated nursing students for accepting others' critical points of view to develop themselves in the light of it. Then demonstrated examples for self-evaluation in front of nursing students and ask them to re-demonstrate it at home. In addition, the researchers provided detailed explanation about (a) concept of self-esteem, (b) methods to improve self-esteem through encouraging nursing students to (1) Strength his/her relation with god. (2) Replace negative thoughts with positive ones. (3) Stay away from negative people. (4) Discover his/her talent and develop it. (5) Maintain body language that express his/her self-esteem e.g., head up and back straight, wear tidy and clean clothes, shake people with confidence and power. (6) Show balance in judging situations without over or under estimation. (7) Gain different skills and openness in dealing with people.

Day III: Session 1: Assertive behavior

The researchers provided detailed explanation about (1) concept of assertiveness, importance of assertiveness for nursing students. (2) Difference between passive, aggressive, passive-aggressive and assertive behavior. (3) Individual's basic rights of assertive behavior. (4) How to say "No" assertively. (5) How to construct a request assertively. (6) How to respond, provide disapproval assertively and offer constructive disapproval. (7) Handle and express anger assertively. (8) How to provide and accept recommendations assertively; and how to make justification assertively. Likewise, the researchers encouraged nursing students to train themselves in the followings: (a) Reject in clear terms with using positive phrases which enable other people to understand that

you said “no”.(b) Try to express your emotions and inner feelings frankly and clearly; (c) Use strict, firm words and Keep the tone of voice steady and elevated. Then the researcher asks students to repeat these skills and apply it in their daily life.

Day III: Session 2: Dealing with bullying phenomenon

It focused on different steps to explain how to manage bullying phenomenon as (1) Put your hands high to not make an obstacle between you and the bully. (2) Say a short sentence to express your rejection, something like: 'Please stop that helps you stand against these behaviors. (3) Take a stand and show that you are not afraid, this trick may not work immediately, but repeating this behavior and showing your self-confidence and calm will make the bully distract you as a victim. (4) Don't take what the bully says personally, it's just intended to destroy you psychologically. (5) Do not respond with similar actions, otherwise things will get worse and you will eventually be hurt instead of bullied.

Day IV: Session 1: Continue dealing with bullying phenomenon

It concerned with the detailed explanation about ways that help nursing students to confront bullying behavior as (1) Write down all the bullying incidents you have experienced, keep the evidence and make assured that a witness is next to you to support your complaint later. (2) Raise your voice, and remember that you are not alone. (3) Tell the bully that you intend to take legal action to stop the harassment. (4) Evaluate yourself continually, especially if you are a victim of harassment and psychological violence. (5) Assess your strengths to improve self-confidence, and weaknesses should be seen as a chance for improvement and change. (6) Try to get close to the people who share your welfares and encourage you to trust yourself.

Day IV: Session 2: Closing and post-test

The researchers appreciated all nursing students for their presence and completing the program sessions. The post-test was given to them to investigate the effectiveness of a planned bullying protective program on self-efficacy and self-esteem among nursing student in the clinical setting using General Self-Efficacy Scale (GSE) and Rosenberg's Global Self-esteem Scale for all nursing students.

Final session for the follow up-test

The researchers welcomed all participants and appreciated them for their attendance. A follow-up test was done using General Self-Efficacy Scale and Rosenberg's Global Self-esteem Scale to investigate the effect of applying bullying protective program on self-efficacy and self-esteem among nursing students.

Data Analysis

Data were revised, coded, entered, analyzed and tabulated using Statistical Package of Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25. Both descriptive statistics (frequency, percentage, mean and standard deviation) and inferential statistics (Pearson correlation test, chi-square test were used appropriately according to the type of variables. The level of statistical significance was established in 0.05.

RESULTS

As presented in Table1, the mean age of nursing students was (22.0±0.64) years, (71.9%) of them were female, more than two thirds of them (68.3%) were from rural area and most of them (85.1%) were single.

As pointed in Figure 1, there were statistically significant differences in self-efficacy levels before and after the training program; where after implementing the bullying protective program, slightly more than three quarters of nursing students (76.90%) had high level of self-efficacy and none of them had low level of self-efficacy as compared to before the program, where only (0.9%) had high level of self-efficacy, more than half (57%) of nursing students had low level of self-efficacy.

As shown in Figure 2, there were statistically significant difference in self-esteem levels before and after the applying program; where after implementing the training program, approximately about three quarters of nursing students (74.7%) had high level of self-esteem, while, none of them had low level of self-esteem as compared to before the program, none of them had high level of self-esteem and (19 %) had low level of self-esteem and (81%) of them had normal (moderate) level of self-esteem.

As presented in Table 2, there is a highly statistical significant improvement in the different levels of self-efficacy immediately after bullying protective program and after 3 months (follow-up test) among nursing students compared to before the program where ($p = 0.000$).

As illustrated in Table 3, there is a highly statistical

Table 1. Socio- demographic characteristics of participant nursing students (N = 221).

Characters:	N.	%
Age (years):		
20- 21 years	39	17.6
22-23 years	182	82.4
Mean ± SD		22.0±0.64 years
Gender:		
Female	159	71.9
Male	62	28.1
Residence:		
Urban	70	31.7
Rural	151	68.3
Marital Status:		
Single	188	85.1
Married	33	14.9
Total	221	100

Figure 1. Self-efficacy levels before and after the training program among nursing students (N=221).

Figure 2. Self-esteem levels before and after implementing the program among nursing students (N=221).

Table 2. Self-efficacy levels among nursing students before, after bullying protective program and after 3months follow-up (N=221).

Levels of self-efficacy	Before program		After program		Follow-up test		Test of sig.	P value
	N.	%	N.	%	N.	%		
Low self-efficacy	126	57.0	0	0	0	0	Mc Neymar test = 94.3	P=0.000 HS
Normal self-efficacy	93	42.1	51	23.1	124	56.1		
High self- efficacy	2	0.9	170	76.9	97	43.9		
Total	221	100	221	100	221	100		

Table 3. Self- esteem levels among nursing students before, after bullying protective program and after 3months follow-up (N=221)

-Levels of self esteem	Before program		After program		Follow-up test		Test of sig.	P value
	N.	%	N.	%	N.	%		
Low self-esteem	42	19.0	0	0	0	0	Mc Neymar test = 60.7	P=0.000 HS
Normal self-esteem	179	81.0	56	25.3	124	56.1		
High self- esteem	0	0	165	74.7	97	43.9		
Total	221	100	221	100	221	100		

significant improvement in the different levels of self-esteem immediately after bullying protective program and after 3 months (follow-up test) among nursing students compared to before the program where (p = 0.000).

DISCUSSION

Bullying represent a public health issue that can prone

victims to severe physical and psychosocial health problems that requires the time and attention of parents, teachers, school administrators, health care providers and policy makers (Frederick and Suzanne, 2016). Students experienced more covert bullying such as bullying from other students and staff in academic setting, often in the form of extreme criticism, mockery, and spreading rumors and harassment through social media. This bullying increased students' anxiety and stress level, reduced self-esteem and perceived competence, and

eventually led to questions about future career choices (Kang, 2018). Moreover, Cooper et al. (2011) mentioned that nursing students have the main hazard of suffering undesirable behaviors since they are younger nurses, less experienced, less educated, constant ward changes and the challenge of meeting new environment. Self-efficacy in senior nursing students aids them to feel proficient in fulfilling the entry level in clinical fields and to accept this challenging role. Self-efficacy is a good indicator to anticipate nursing students' performance in clinical practice (Zengin et al., 2014). In addition, self-efficacy is an important factor in career development, especially in academic and professional interests, selection, and performance, along with goals and outcomes (Nalipay and Alfons, 2018).

The existing finding revealed that more than half (57%) of nursing students had low level of self-efficacy and (42.1%) of them had normal (moderate) level of self-efficacy and only (0.9%) had high level of self-efficacy before implementing the protective program. These results were supported by Kassem et al., (2015) who mentioned that more than half of nursing students had mild self-efficacy. Moreover, these results were reinforced by Richard and Carrie (2018) who reported that overall self-efficacy levels are still in a low level among nursing students.

However, the present results were contradicted with Viswam-Athira et al. (2017) who declared that (53.07%) of nursing students had high general self-efficacy and (46.92%) of them had low self-efficacy. In addition, this result was contrasted with Sarikoc and Oksuz (2017) who revealed that nursing students had higher positive general self-efficacy. Likewise, the study result was disagreed with Maraghi et al. (2018) who stated that a significant percentage of students had average to high academic self-efficacy (75.8% average and 22.1% High).

These differences may be attributed to differences in societies and cultures, lack of experience and skills, frequent change of teachers and training areas, and high academic loads. In addition to inadequate preparation of students before entering clinical settings, low socio-economic status, and lack of financial and moral support for nursing students in our developing countries. Additionally, teaching four major specialties in the fourth year, such as mental health nursing, nursing administration, community health nursing and geriatric nursing, this makes students overloaded, and unable to master these subjects, which in turn leads to lack of self-confidence and subsequently self-efficacy.

The existing findings displayed that most nursing students (81%) had normal (moderate) level of self-esteem before implementing the training program. This finding was supported by Ribeiro et al., (2020) who declared that the self-esteem in the pre-test was moderate (average 23.48). Also, this finding was consistent with other studies conducted among nursing students (Fawzy et al. (2020), Ibrahim (2015) and

Dabirian et al. (2016) who stated that the levels of self-esteem among nursing students were moderate. Moreover, the study results were in the same line with Belsiyal (2015) who reported that two thirds of nursing students have moderate level of self-esteem while one third of them have low level of self-esteem. Additionally, these findings were in the same track with Kumar (2020) who reported that (84.7 %) of nursing students had normal level of self-esteem.

However, these findings was contradicted with Chalise and Pandey (2015) who indicated that (78 %) of nursing students had low level of self-esteem. Also, the outcomes of this study were contrasted with the results of other studies conducted among nursing students (Furegato et al. (2008), Megahed and Mohammad (2014) and Azizi et al. (2013) who exhibited that the self-esteem of the majority of nursing students was at low level. In addition, Ebrahim and Elrefaey (2018) reported that the majority of nursing students had low to moderate levels of self-esteem.

The existing findings revealed that nursing students experienced moderate to low level of self-esteem. These findings were disagreed with Fawzy et al. (2020) who mentioned that levels of self-esteem among nursing students was moderate and high. Also, these results were contradicted with the results of other studies conducted among nursing students (Ibrahim (2015) and Dabirian et al. (2016) who found the level of self-esteem among nursing students were moderate to high. The differences from the present study findings may be owing to differences in societies and cultures, lack of attractiveness of community health nursing curriculum, especially home visits, and the harassment experienced by students during these visits which in turn leads to lowering their self-esteem.

The existing study's findings revealed that there were a highly statistical significant improvement in the different levels of both self-efficacy and self-esteem immediately after bullying protective program and after 3 months (follow-up test) among nursing students compared to before the program where ($p = 0.000$). This indicates that the bullying protective program was more effective for nursing students; which reflects that the sessions of the program were in the interest and needs of nursing students, and therefore had a positive impact on increasing students' self-confidence and self-efficacy and improving their ability to be safe in the face of this violent phenomenon.

The present findings displayed that there were great improvements in the self-efficacy levels after implementing bullying protective program. From the researchers' point of view, this finding can be explained by the fact that nursing students who have received a bullying protective program that includes training sessions on improving self-awareness, assertive communication skills and self-esteem development are able to cope with the problems and pressures they face

and are able to deal with their teachers and colleagues in a professional manner, which in turn increases their self-effectiveness and academic performance. The outcomes of the existing study were supported by Kassem et al. (2015) who stated that there was a significance relationship between bullying behavior and general self-efficacy among the studied nursing students. Another study demonstrated that after the training period, the mean self-efficacy score increased from (13.76 ± 3.02) to (14.34 ± 3.47) , and the group training had a significant positive impact on self-efficacy of subjects (Shokhmgar et al., 2018). Moreover, bullying others was associated with lower health-related quality of life, and that a higher general self-efficacy was associated with better health-related quality of life (Haraldstad et al., 2019).

The present study's findings revealed a significant improvement in the levels of self-esteem in the post test and follow-up test compared to pretest; which reflect the comprehensiveness of the program sessions which include concept, causes, forms, signs and side effect of bullying behavior. In addition to, ways to protect against bullying behavior as improving self-esteem, training in assertive behavior and how to deal with the bullying phenomenon, which in turn promotes their self-esteem and self-confidence in their ability to confront the challenges of life. They can achieve successes by coping with educational problems and increase their success potentials. In the same line, Kang (2018) reported that "nursing students' bullying experiences should be considered seriously as they have a long-term impact on their self-esteem and identity as well as negatively affecting their future career as a nurse". Moreover, an inverse relationship exists between self-esteem and experiences of bullying behaviors. Those with higher mean bullying scores had lower mean self-esteem score (Clarke, 2009). Furthermore, one of the main consequences of bullying in the workplace is nurses who quit their jobs or the nursing profession (Stagg et al., 2011). Nurses with low self-esteem are at greater risk of bullying in the workplace, and their degree of depression is significantly higher Meng et al., (2017) and Nie et al., (2013) found that "workplace bullying was significantly and negatively correlated with nurses' self-esteem". "Workplace bullying has a significant predictive effect on self-esteem. The more bullying the nurses experience, the lower is the level of self-esteem".

Finally, some students report leaving nursing school as a consequence of bullying. Many types of bullying occur in class or clinical settings within and between student and faculty groups (Hopkins et al., 2014). Rudeness, yelling, and making disparaging remarks are the most frequent types of bullying reported by students in nursing school (Seibe and Fehr, 2018). "Studies have created diverse reports regarding the causes of bullying for students; some report that nurse-to-student bullying is most prevalent, others cite faculty-to-student bullying as

the most problematic and yet others claim that colleagues can be very hostile to each other (Pope, 2010)".

LIMITATIONS

The most prominent limitation of the existing study was that all data were obtained by self-reported cross-sectional surveys, which could lead to a common method difference between the predictor variable and outcome variables. Moreover, the sample was taken from one squad from one nursing collage only. Therefore, selecting sample from different nursing collages recommended for future studies to popularize the findings.

CONCLUSION

The current study's findings revealed that there were a highly statistical significant improvement in the different levels of both self-esteem and self-efficacy immediately after bullying protective program and after 3 months (follow-up test) among nursing students compared to before the program where ($p = 0.000$). Moreover, implementing the bullying protective program has a positive effect on improving self-efficacy and self-esteem of nursing students.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In the light of study findings, the following recommendations were yielded:

1. In the existing study, we used self-reported questionnaires to assess self-efficacy and self-esteem and students' response was subjective, but the use of personal interviews may be more objective and impartial response.
2. Nursing curricula should incorporate the concept of bullying and how to confront it in a professional manner. Also, the nursing college should set policies to eradicate the occurrence of bullying in the workplace, which creates a positive impact on the learning environment and the nursing profession as a whole.
3. Further studies are necessary with a greater sample size extending across diverse governmental and private colleges in various governorates to generalize the findings.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

We would like to thank all the participant nursing students for their cooperation and assistance while collecting data.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Source of funding

This research has not received any funding.

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